

Impact Factor: 5.19

ISSN: 2181-0664

DOI: 10.26739/2181-0664

www.tadqiqot.uz

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

Volume 4, Issue 3

2023

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

4 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

УЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

ТОМ 4, НОМЕР 3

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 3

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ | UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL
№3 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-0664-2023-3>

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STUDY OF THE HYPOLIPIDEMIC AND ANTI-INFLAMMATORY EFFECTS OF “YANTAK” DECOCTION IN PATIENTS WITH CORONARY HEART DISEASE AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF STANDARD THERAPY

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7988666>

ABSTRACT

This article presents data on the use of "Yantak" decoction against the background of standard therapy of stable forms of coronary heart disease with hypolipidemic (by reducing the parameters of the atherogenic fraction and the tendency to increase the anti-atherogenic fraction), anti-inflammatory effects (trends in reducing the level of IL - 6 and highly specific CRP), and also demonstrated positive dynamics of clinical indicators to reduce the number of angina attacks and the need for nitroglycerin tablets. The dynamics of observation of patients with stable forms of coronary heart disease according to the results of the study showed an improvement in the parameters of the "quality of life" according to the results of the SF-36 questionnaire, this served as an additional condition for increasing adherence to therapy. The study's results showed the effectiveness of phytotherapy, which allowed, against the background of standard therapy, to improve the clinical prognosis in patients with high cardiovascular risk.

Keywords: coronary heart disease, lipid profile, anti-inflammatory effect, quality of life, traditional medicine.

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ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ГИПОЛИПДЕМИЧЕСКОГО И ПРОТИВОВОСПАЛИТЕЛЬНОГО ЭФФЕКТА ОТВАРА «ЯНТАК» У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ИШЕМИЧЕСКОЙ БОЛЕЗНЬЮ СЕРДЦА НА ФОНЕ СТАНДАРТНОЙ ТЕРАПИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье приведены данные применения отвара «Янтак» на фоне стандартной терапии стабильных форм ишемической болезни сердца по отношению гипوليцидемической (по снижению параметров атерогенной фракции и тенденции повышению антиатерогенной фракции), противовоспалительный эффекты (тенденции снижения уровня ИЛ -6 и высокоспецифического СРБ), а также продемонстрировало положительную динамику клинических показателей по снижению количества приступов стенокардии и потребности в таблетках нитроглицерина. Динамика наблюдения за пациентами со стабильными формами ишемической болезни сердца по результатам проведенного исследования показала улучшение параметров «качества жизни» по результатам опросника SF-36, это послужило дополнительным условием для повышения приверженности к терапии. Результаты исследования показали эффективность фитотерапии, позволившую на фоне стандартной терапии улучшить клинический прогноз у пациентов высокого сердечно-сосудистого риска.

Ключевые слова: ишемическая болезнь сердца, липидный профиль, противовоспалительный эффект, качество жизни, народная медицина.

**Tulabaeva G. M.,
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Tibbiyot xodimlarining kasbiy malakasini rivijlantirish markazi,
kardiologiya va gerontologiya, intervension
kardiologiya va aritmologiya kursi bilan kafedra.

YURAK ISHEMIK KASALLIGILI BEMORLARDA "YUNTAK" DAMLAMASINING STANDART TERAPIYA FONIDA GIPOLIPIDEMIK VA YALLIG'LANISHGA QARSHI TA'SIRINI O'RGANISH

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada gipolipidemik (aterogen fraktsiya parametrlarini pasaytirish va antiaterogen fraktsiyani ko'paytirish tendentsiyasi orqali), yallig'lanishga qarshi ta'sirga nisbatan yurak ishemik kasalliklarining barqaror shakllari uchun standart terapiya fonida Yantak damlamasidan foydalanish to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. (IL-6 va yuqori o'ziga xos CRP darajasini pasaytirish tendentsiyalari), shuningdek, stenokardiya xurujlari sonini va nitroglicerol tabletkalariga bo'lgan ehtiyojni kamaytirish uchun klinik ko'rsatkichlarda ijobiy tendentsiyani ko'rsatdi. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra yurak-qon tomir kasalliklarining barqaror shakllari bo'lgan bemorlarni kuzatish dinamikasi SF-36 so'rovnomasi natijalariga ko'ra "hayot sifati" ko'rsatkichlarining yaxshilanganligini ko'rsatdi, bu esa terapiyaga rioya qilishni oshirish uchun qo'shimcha shart bo'lib xizmat qildi.. Tadqiqot natijalari o'simlik dori-darmonlarining samaradorligini ko'rsatdi, bu standart terapiya fonida yuqori yurak-qon tomir xavfi bo'lgan bemorlarda klinik prognozni yaxshilashga imkon berdi.

Kalit so'zlar: yurak ishemik kasalligi, lipid profili, yallig'lanishga qarshi ta'sir, hayot sifati, an'anaviy tibbiyot.

Relevance. Although information about the use of medicinal properties of plants has its roots in ancient times, the relevance of medicinal plants in recent decades has increased significantly. This is due to the many advantages of using phytopreparations compared to synthetic medicines [5]. The biological affinity between herbal remedies and the human body, the low toxicity and the possibility of long-term use without significant side effects, and their complex effects on the body broaden our understanding concerning improving compliance to therapy [1]. Herbal remedies stimulate the

protective forces of the body, increasing its efficiency and resistance to adverse external factors [3]. In this regard, pharmaceutical science's most important task is to create medicines from medicinal plant raw materials of adaptogenic action, whose role in medicine and other areas of human activity is significant. Now, there are all preconditions for traditional medicine, as a branch of knowledge and a component of national culture, was formed in an independent scientific direction, lying at the joint of such sciences as physiology and ecology, taking into account knowledge of features of formation of national cultures [6].

Even though many unconventional methods are quite effective, today, there is still a problem with the lack of experience among specialists and the low adherence of patients to their use [1, 3].

Traditional medicine is an amazing gift that nature has for treating our bodies. The healing properties of folk medicine that medicinal plants possess are truly inexhaustible and hold much that we do not yet know, but which will be even more effective in treating disease, the support of folk medicine [3]. It should be noted that the World Health Organization (WHO) has the most active position on traditional and traditional medicine. The WHO's position was expressed in a Strategy developed in 2014, according to which traditional medicine is an important and often underestimated part of the health care system [3]. This document describes traditional medicines widely used in Asian countries, such as Ayurveda, Chinese and Arabic medicine, and traditional medicine (indigenous medicine). WHO has set out to increase the recognition of traditional medicine to support and integrate it into national health systems. Many WHO Member States and partners in traditional medicine (United Nations organizations, international organizations, non-governmental organizations, including global and national professional associations) have expressed their willingness to participate in its implementation.

The commitment to the study, application and use of traditional medicines from different countries as well as of Oriental traditional medicines, offering their distribution in different regions (taking into account the initial cheapness in their countries) led to their active development in Asian countries and their subsequent spread worldwide.

Data from numerous researches have proved high efficiency on application of herbal remedies isolated from plants with application of folk recipes, their relative safety, high bioavailability, less toxicity, high bioequivalence and accordingly high commitment with complex preferential influence on all organisms as a whole is shown.

Thus, using the experience of traditional medicine, it is possible to carry out both the prevention of diseases and to apply complex therapy together with traditional medicines [1].

The decoction - tea produced from camel's thorn, Yantak, a sugar-free and GMO-free beverage, studied in the present study, which has several positive effects, is recommended not only for the treatment but also for the prevention of disease. All species of camel's thorns are shown to be effective, highly nutritious fodder plants. Their above-ground parts, especially when young, are rich in vitamin C, which makes them a valuable vitamin product considering the leaves' nutritional properties and especially their sugar content. Flavinoids contained in camel's stickleback extract can reduce glycaemia levels and have a hypolipidemic effect mainly by inhibiting the cascade - oxidative stress, which has been proven in vivo studies [4, 7].

Besides, the fibrinolytic properties of Camel's stickleback extracts have been revealed [4, 5]. Experimental studies have shown reliable efficacy compared with taxifolinum with the regression of initial stages of aortic atherosclerosis in experimental models [2].

Objective: To study the hypolipidemic, anti-inflammatory effects of decoction of the herb camel's-thorn (Yantak tea) in patients with stable forms of coronary heart disease.

Materials and Methods: 80 (100%) patients with stable forms of coronary heart disease (CHD), especially with stable angina pectoris I-II and III, including 30 (37,5%) women and 50 (62,5%) men aged from 55 to 72 years ($63,4 \pm 7,1$) were included in the investigation. Among the examined patients, 23 (28,8%) patients had myocardial infarction from 7 to 10 months, according to the anamnesis data. The mean duration of CHD was $8,2 \pm 2,5$ years, stable angina I-II class was observed in 52 (65%) and III class in 28 (35%) patients. The diagnosis was verified according to WHO Expert Committee recommendations and its severity - according to the classification of

Canadian Heart Association. According to the study protocol, risk factors for cardiovascular diseases and their complications were identified in all patients included in the study (Table 1.)

Table 1.

Analysis of risk factors for CHD

№	Indicators under study	N (abs)	%
1	Arterial hypertension	63	79
2	Smoking	33	41,3
3	Hypodynamia	28	35
4	Obesity	19	23,8
5	Alcohol	8	10
6	Type 2 diabetes	23	29
7	Anxiety and depression	29	36,3

At the evaluation of anamnestic information, the risk factors of CHD have been revealed in all patients, including arterial hypertension in 63 (79%), permanent psycho-emotional pressure with manifestations of the anxious-depressive syndrome in 29 (36,3%), smoking in 33 (41,3%) of examined patients, obesity in 19 (23,8%), hypodynamia in 28 (35%), diabetes mellitus in 23 (28,8%), alcohol abuse in 8 patients (10%).

The exclusion criteria were life-threatening cardiac arrhythmias, atrioventricular block of II, III-degree, paroxysmal tachycardia, severe liver and kidney damage and malignant neoplasms.

Patients were divided into 2 groups according to their treatment by random sampling: The 1 group (basic - 40) against the background of the essential therapy was given "Yantac" from 0.5 to 1.0 litres a day, and the 2 groups (control - 40) received only basic therapy (beta-blockers, hypolipidemic agents, calcium antagonists, antiplatelet agents, and if necessary short-acting nitrates as an antianginal agent). The study groups were comparable in age, sex, disease duration and comorbidities.

All patients at study inclusion and after 2 months of therapy underwent a comprehensive, dynamic, clinical and instrumental examination. Blood lipid spectrum, coagulogram, urea, creatinine, levels of interleukin 6 (IL-6) and high specific C-reactive protein were analyzed, hemodynamics was checked by measuring blood pressure (BP), 12-lead electrocardiography (ECG), treadmill test ECG, standard transthoracic echocardiography (EchoCG), and quality of life scores were determined using the Medical Outcomes Study 36-Item Short Form Health Survey (SF-36) [10]. This questionnaire consists of 8 scales and assesses 2 main components of QOL: psychological and physical. The first includes 4 scales: observation, social observation, role-emotional observation, and psychological health. The second component is also represented by 4 scales: physical action, physical role-action, pain and general health. The SF-36 is widely used in population studies around the world. Thus, the questionnaire allows the assessment of quality-of-life indicators according to 8 criteria: GH - general health, PF - physical functioning, SF - social functioning, RP - physical state, RE - emotional state, BP - pain intensity, VT - life activity, MH - self-assessment of mental health.

Statistical analysis was performed using the SPSS 11.0 statistical software package. The findings were described as $M \pm SD$ (M is the arithmetic mean, SD is the standard deviation) or $M \pm m$ (m is the standard error of the mean). Statistical significance of the results obtained in comparing the mean values was determined by Student's t-test with the calculation of the probability of error (P) when testing for normality of distribution using standard methods.

Research results and discussion. The analysis of the received data in the course of the 2-month therapy in both groups showed positive dynamics on the clinical status and the data of laboratory-instrumental indices, at the same time the significant tendency of positive dynamics was noted in the patients of the main group. Against the background of 2-month therapy with the addition of decoction "Yantak" to the standard anti-ischemic, anti-anginal therapy of CHD, positive dynamics in the reduction of systolic (MAP) and diastolic (DAP) in the dynamic observation groups with a significant reduction of BP level in the main group was noted (Fig.1).

Note: * $p < 0.05$ reliability of differences concerning baseline data, ISAD-baseline systolic BP, PTSAD-after-therapy systolic BP, IDAD-baseline diastolic BP, PTCAD-after-therapy diastolic BP

Figure 1. SBP and DBP levels before and after therapy

A reduction in the levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines in the blood, particularly IL-6, has also been observed in the follow-up,

Note: * $p < 0,05$, ** $p < 0,01$ reliability of differences with the initial data, IL-6 - initial IL-6, ATIL-6 – after therapy IL-6 therapy, BS-protein – baseline S protein, ATS-protein - after S-protein therapy.

Figure 2: Indexes of IL-6 and C-reactive protein before and after therapy

(Figure 2) as well as indicators of chronic inflammation with myocardial damage by the values of high-sensitivity C-reactive protein.

The therapy dynamics in patients in both groups demonstrated a positive hypolipidemic effect (against the background of standard therapy for CHD). The results showed a 21% ($p < 0,01$) decrease in total cholesterol level in the main group, 18% in the control group ($p < 0,05$), a 20% decrease in LDL level ($p < 0,05$) in the main group and 8% in the control group. A relative increase in HDL content by 10% ($p < 0,05$) in the main group and by 6,5% in the control group has been observed. The dynamics of the indexes of lipid profile in the patients of the main group presented (picture 3) shows

that addition of "Yantak" decoction to the basic therapy has a positive effect on the parameters of lipid exchange in terms of a reliable reduction of general cholesterol with a tendency to reduce other atherogenicity indexes, compared to the data obtained in the control group (picture 4).

Note: * $p < 0.01$ significant difference from baseline

Figure 3: Blood lipid profile in the main group

Note: * $p < 0.05$ reliability of differences from baseline

Figure 4. The blood lipid spectrum in the control group patients

In the main group, 23 (57,5%) patients had fasting hyperglycemia ($7,8 \pm 2,3$ mMol/l), 11 (27,5%) patients had anamnestic data on the presence of diabetes mellitus type 2. The dynamics of the 2-month treatment showed a tendency to reduce the level of jejunal glycemia (6.2 ± 1.5 mMol/l).

During the period of observation in the course of 2-month standard treatment with the subsequent additional therapy by "Yantak" decoction, unreliable dynamics of improvement of intracardiac hemodynamics parameters (end-diastolic and end-systolic volume index) and remodeling indices (relative wall thickness and LV sphericity index (integral index of intracardiac hemodynamics - LV ejection fraction EF (in the main group from 54 to 58% and in the control group from 55 to 56%) has been registered.

The next aspect of this study was the assessment of quality of life in patients with stable forms of coronary artery disease. It is known that the study of quality of life in patients with cardiovascular

pathologies is of great scientific and practical interest nowadays to assess the effectiveness of diagnostic, therapeutic and preventive measures. The quality of life indicators and characteristics of the disease picture change over time depending on the patient's condition, allowing monitoring of the ongoing treatment and, if necessary, its correction. The quality of life indicators for the SF-36 questionnaire in the main and control groups studied in this study showed the lowest quality of life in both groups. Reduced values of RF marked it- 18.0 ± 3.1 and 16.9 ± 2.5 , RE (25.7 ± 2.3 and 31.4 ± 4.3), PF in the main group was 50.5 ± 2.0 and 53.6 ± 2.9 in the control group. GH, SF, BP, and VT values varied between 42 and 45.

In patients of the main group after 2 months of treatment, a positive dynamics of improvement of quality of life was marked according to many scales, which was characterized by significant increase of parameters on RF scale (from $6,2 \pm 1,1$ to $18,8 \pm 1,8$), GH (from $41 \pm 3,2$ to $51 \pm 2,7$), VT (from $3,0 \pm 4,2$ to $55, \pm 2,9$) in comparison with control group.

Note: * $p < 0.05$ significance of differences with baseline AP- angina pectoris, TNT- taking nitroglycerin tablets

Figure 5. HR, AP, TNT before and after treatment (study group).

Undoubtedly, the improvement of quality of life parameters has a positive impact on the course of the underlying disease, especially on its clinical course in the main group (Fig 5) and the control group (Fig 6), which is reflected in a reduction of angina pectoris attacks (AP), the need for nitroglycerin tablets (TNT) and hemodynamic parameters (HR) respectively.

The QOL scores and patients' self-perception of their health status are powerful predictors of life expectancy.

Note: * $p < 0.05$ significant difference from baseline PAS-attacks of angina, PTN-nitroglycerin tablets

Figure 6. HR, AP, TNT before and after treatment (control group)

In addition, additional effects have been studied. So, for example, in patients in the main group: 12 (30%) patients had constipation tendencies. After regular application of "Yantak" broth, the stool became regular in 9 (75%) of them, 8 (20%) patients marked night itching, which in dynamics of treatment decreased in intensity. Also, sleep disorders were marked in 7 (17,5%) patients. In dynamics, in 5 (71%), sleep became quiet, though possibly connected with improved life quality and decreased depressive disorders.

Good decoction "Yantak" tolerability was noted in all examined patients and no negative adverse reactions were detected.

Conclusions: application of the decoction "Yantak" against the background of the standard therapy of the stable forms of coronary heart disease showed potentiation of hypolipidemic efficiency (by the decrease of atherogenic fraction parameters and tendency to increase of the antiatherogenic fraction), showed anti-inflammatory effect (by the tendency to decrease of IL-6 and high specific SRB level), and also demonstrated positive dynamics of clinical parameters by reducing the number of angina attacks and need for nitroglycerin tablets.

The dynamics of observation of patients with stable forms of CHD according to the results of the study showed an improvement in the parameters of "quality of life" according to the SF-36 questionnaire, first of all, the patients' complaints decreased, their functional abilities increased, patients' perception of their life changes related to the disease, etc., and this in turn can be an additional condition to determine the degree of objectivity of the clinical prognosis and effectiveness of the therapy, thereby synergy between methods of folk and standard therapy.

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UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 3

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